

**DUALS OF THE BERNOULLI NUMBERS AND POLYNOMIALS
AND THE EULER NUMBERS AND POLYNOMIALS**

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Abstract

A sequence inverse relationship can be defined by a pair of infinite inverse matrices. If those two matrices are the same, they define a dual relationship. Presented here is a unified approach to construct dual relationships using pseudo-Riordan involutions. Then we give four dual relationships for the Bernoulli numbers and the Euler numbers, from which the corresponding dual sequences of the Bernoulli polynomials and the Euler polynomials are constructed. Some applications in the construction of identities of the Bernoulli numbers and polynomials and the Euler numbers and polynomials are discussed based on the dual relationships.

1. Introduction

Krattenthaler defines a class of matrix inverses in [29], which has numerous famous special cases presented by Gould and Hsu [16], Carlitz [5], Bressoud [2], Chu and Hsu [10], Ma[32], etc. Hsu, Shiue, and one of the authors of this paper study Riordan matrix inverses in [26]. Let infinite low triangle matrices $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$ and $(\bar{d}_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$ be *matrix inverses*. Then a *sequence inverse relationship* can be defined by

$$f_n = \sum_{k=0}^n d_{n,k} g_k \text{ if and only if } g_n = \sum_{k=0}^n \bar{d}_{n,k} f_k, \quad (1)$$

where the sequences $(f_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(g_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are called the *inverse sequences* with respect to the inverse matrices $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$ and $(\bar{d}_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$. If $d_{n,k} = \bar{d}_{n,k}$, i.e.,

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$(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$ is self-inverse, then $(f_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(g_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are said to be a pair of *dual sequences* (or they are dual to each other) with respect to the self-inverse matrix $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$. In other words, $\{f_n\}$ and $\{g_n\}$ satisfy

$$f_n = \sum_{k=0}^n d_{n,k} g_k \text{ if and only if } g_n = \sum_{k=0}^n d_{n,k} f_k. \tag{2}$$

If there exists a sequence $(f_n)_{n \geq 0}$ that is dual to itself with respect to a self-inverse matrix $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$, i.e.,

$$f_n = \sum_{k=0}^n d_{n,k} f_k, \tag{3}$$

then $(f_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is called a *self-dual sequence* with respect to the matrix $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$.

Let $d_{n,k} = \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k$. Then $(d_{n,k})_{0 \leq k \leq n}$ is a self-inverse matrix because

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{k}{j} (-1)^{k+j} = \delta_{n,j},$$

where $\delta_{n,j}$ is the Kronecker symbol. Let $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence of complex numbers. Then $(a_n^*)_{n \geq 0}$ defined by

$$a_n^* = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k a_k \tag{4}$$

is the dual sequence of $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ with respect to $\left(\binom{n}{k} (-1)^k\right)$ (see, for example, Graham, Knuth, and Patashnik [17]). Hence,

$$a_n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k a_k^*. \tag{5}$$

Note that $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(a_n^*)_{n \geq 0}$ are a pair of inverse sequences with $(a_n^*)^* = a_n$. If $a_n^* = a_n$, then $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is called a *self-dual sequence* (see Z. W. Sun [51]). For instance, the following number sequences are self-dual sequences with respect to the dual relationship (4) (see, for example, Z. H. Sun [51]):

$$\left(\frac{1}{2^n}\right), \left(\frac{1}{\binom{n+2m-1}{m}}\right), ((-1)^n B_n), (L_n), (nF_{n-1}),$$

where (B_n) , (L_n) , and (F_n) are the Bernoulli number sequence, Lucas number sequence, and Fibonacci number sequence, respectively.

The Bernoulli polynomials $B_n(x)$ and the Euler polynomials $E_n(x)$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots$ are defined by

$$\frac{te^{xt}}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_n(x) \frac{t^n}{n!} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{2e^{xt}}{e^t + 1} = \sum_{n \geq 0} E_n(x) \frac{t^n}{n!}. \tag{6}$$

The Bernoulli numbers B_n and the Euler numbers E_n for $n = 0, 1, \dots$ are defined by

$$B_n = B_n(0) \quad \text{and} \quad E_n = 2^n E_n\left(\frac{1}{2}\right). \tag{7}$$

Many articles are scattered widely in books and journals on the Bernoulli numbers B_n , the Bernoulli polynomials $B_n(x)$, the Euler numbers E_n , and the Euler polynomials $E_n(x)$. They can be studied by means of the following binomial expressions connecting them:

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k x^{n-k} \quad \text{and} \tag{8}$$

$$E_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-k} \frac{E_k}{2^k}, \quad n \geq 0, \tag{9}$$

where $E_k = 2^k E_k(1/2)$. This topic has brought much attention from researchers working in combinatorics, number theory, approximation theory, etc. There are numerous results involving identities for the Bernoulli and the Euler numbers and polynomials. Many well-known results can be found in Buijs, Carrasquel-Vera and Murillo [3], Dilcher [13], Gessel [14], Pan and Sun [39], Miki [36], Sun [51], Sun [52], Sun and Pan [53], etc. Some of the applications of our dual Bernoulli and Euler numbers and polynomials shown below are inspired by those results, particularly [39, 51, 52].

This paper will study the duals of the Bernoulli number sequence and the Euler number sequence with respect to $\left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^k\right)$ and other self-inverse matrices. The dual sequence of $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$, with respect to $\left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^k\right)$, is denoted by $(B_n^*)_{n \geq 0}$ and the corresponding *dual Bernoulli polynomials*, denoted by $(B_n^*(x))_{n \geq 0}$, are defined similarly to (8) by using the duals of sequences $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$, i.e.,

$$B_n^*(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k^* x^{n-k}, \quad n \geq 0, \tag{10}$$

where B_n^* are the *duals of the Bernoulli numbers* $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$, i.e.,

$$B_n^* = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k B_k, \quad n \geq 0. \tag{11}$$

Hence, there are several questions raised: (1) What is the self-inverse matrix with respect to which the Bernoulli number sequence (B_n) is self-dual? (2) What is the relationship between the self-inverse matrix in (1) and the self-inverse matrix, $\left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^k\right)$, for $\left((-1)^n B_n\right)_{n \geq 0}$? In addition, (3) does there exist a unified approach to construct self-inverse matrices and self-duals with respect to a self-inverse matrix? We will answer those questions by using the Riordan array theory.

Riordan arrays are infinite, lower triangular matrices defined by the generating function of their columns. They form a group, called the *Riordan group* (see Shapiro et al. [48]). Some of the main results on the Riordan group and its application to combinatorial sums and identities can be found in [6]–[9], [11]–[12], [15], [18]–[28], [30]–[31], [33]–[35], [38], [40]–[41], [43]–[47], [49]–[50], [54]–[55], and [57]. Particularly, Merlini et al. [35] survey the method of coefficients in solving a number of combinatorial problems by lending themselves to expression in terms of generating functions. In this paper, they mentioned that using the technique of diagonalization with Riordan arrays allowed them to solve combinatorial inversions, which was studied in [26] by Hsu, Shiue, and one of the authors of this paper. In this paper, we shall use the pseudo-Riordan involution to discuss the dual sequences.

More formally, let us consider the set of formal power series (f.p.s.) $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{R}[[t]]$; the order of $f(t) \in \mathcal{F}$, $f(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k t^k$ ($f_k \in \mathbb{R}$), is the minimal number $r \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $f_r \neq 0$; \mathcal{F}_r is the set of formal power series of order r . It is known that \mathcal{F}_0 is the set of invertible f.p.s. and \mathcal{F}_1 is the set of compositionally invertible f.p.s., that is, the f.p.s. $f(t)$ for which the *compositional inverse* $\bar{f}(t)$ exists such that $f(\bar{f}(t)) = \bar{f}(f(t)) = t$. Let $d(t) \in \mathcal{F}_0$ and $h(t) \in \mathcal{F}_1$. The pair $(d(t), h(t))$ defines the (proper) Riordan array $D = (d_{n,k})_{n,k \in \mathbb{N}} = (d(t), h(t))$ with

$$d_{n,k} = [t^n]d(t)h(t)^k. \tag{12}$$

In other words, D has $d(t)h(t)^k$ as its k th column generating function whose coefficients make-up the entries of column k .

It is immediately known that the usual row-by-column product of two Riordan arrays is also the Riordan array

$$(d_1(t), h_1(t)) * (d_2(t), h_2(t)) = (d_1(t)d_2(h_1(t)), h_2(h_1(t))), \tag{13}$$

where the fundamental theorem of Riordan arrays,

$$(d(t), h(t))f(t) = d(t)f(h(t)), \tag{14}$$

is applied to obtain (13). The Riordan array $I = (1, t)$ is everywhere 0 except that it contains all 1's on the main diagonal; it can be easily proven that I acts as an identity for this product, that is, $(1, t) * (d(t), h(t)) = (d(t), h(t)) * (1, t) = (d(t), h(t))$. From these facts, we deduce a formula for the inverse Riordan array

$$(d(t), h(t))^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{d(\bar{h}(t))}, \bar{h}(t) \right) \tag{15}$$

where $\bar{h}(t)$ is the *compositional inverse* of $h(t)$. In this way, the set \mathcal{R} of proper Riordan arrays forms a group.

From [44] an infinite lower triangular array $[d_{n,k}]_{n,k \in \mathbb{N}} = (d(t), h(t))$, $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, is a Riordan array if and only if a sequence $A = (a_0 \neq 0, a_1, a_2, \dots)$ exists such that

for every $n, k \in \mathbb{N}$ the following holds:

$$d_{n+1,k+1} = a_0 d_{n,k} + a_1 d_{n,k+1} + \cdots + a_n d_{n,n}, \tag{16}$$

which is shown in [27] to be equivalent to

$$h(t) = tA(h(t)). \tag{17}$$

Here, $A(t)$ is the generating function of the A -sequence. In [27, 33] it is also shown that a unique sequence $Z = (z_0, z_1, z_2, \dots)$ exists such that every element in the first column can be expressed as the linear combination

$$d_{n+1,0} = z_0 d_{n,0} + z_1 d_{n,1} + \cdots + z_n d_{n,n}, \tag{18}$$

or equivalently,

$$d(t) = \frac{d_{0,0}}{1 - tZ(h(t))}. \tag{19}$$

We call sequences A and Z the A -(*characterization*) *sequence* and Z -(*characterization*) *sequence* of the Riordan array $(d(t), h(t))$, respectively. And we call the generating functions of A -sequence and Z -sequence the A -*function* and Z -*function*, respectively.

In the next section, we present a unified approach to construct a class of self-inverse matrices. We also include their applications in the construction of dual number sequences and dual polynomial sequences. In Section 3 we shall discuss the algebraic structure of dual number sequences with respect to the dual relationships established in Section 2. Some identities of self-dual number sequences will be found accordingly. In Section 4, more applications of the dual relationships in the construction of identities for dual number sequences will be given.

2. Construction of Self-inverse Matrices and the Corresponding Self-duals

It is clear that a Riordan array $(d(t), h(t))$ and its inverse

$$(d(t), h(t))^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{d(\bar{h}(t))}, \bar{h}(t) \right), \text{ where } \bar{h}(h(t)) = h(\bar{h}(t)) = t,$$

is a pair of inverse matrices. If $(d(t), h(t))^{-1} = (d(t), h(t))$, i.e., $(d(t), h(t))$ is an *involution*, or equivalently, if it has an order of 2, then $(d(t), h(t))$ is a self-inverse matrix. Here, if g is an element of a group G , then the smallest positive integer n , such that g^n equals to the identity e of the group, if it exists, is called the order of g . If no such integer exists, then g is said to have infinite order. It is well-known that (see Shapiro [46]) if we restrict all entries of a Riordan array to be integers,

then any element of finite order in the Riordan group must have order 1 or 2, and each element of order 2 generates a subgroup of order 2. Sprugnoli and one of the authors of this paper find the sequence characterization of Riordan arrays of order 2 in [27].

In the applications to combinatorics, a Riordan array often has nonnegative integer entries and hence it cannot have order 2. Therefore, we consider (see definition, for example, in [7]) an element $R \in \mathcal{R}$ to have pseudo-order 2, i.e., RM has order 2, where $M = (1, -t)$. Those R are called *pseudo-Riordan involutions* or briefly *pseudo-involutions* (see Cameron and Nkwanta [4] and [46]). We now present some sufficient and necessary conditions to identify pseudo-involutions.

Theorem 1. *Let $(d(t), h(t))$ be a pseudo-involution, and let $A(t)$ and $Z(t)$ be the generating functions of the A-sequence and Z-sequence of $(d(t), h(t))$ (i.e., $A(t)$ and $Z(t)$ are the A-function and Z-function, respectively). Then the following statements are equivalent to the statement that the Riordan array $(d(t), h(t))$ is a pseudo-involution:*

- (i) $\pm(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (\pm d(t), -h(t))$ are involutions,
- (ii) $(1, -t)(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (d(t), h(t))^{-1}$, the inverse of $(d(t), h(t))$,
- (iii) $\pm(1, -t)(d(t), h(t)) = (\pm d(-t), h(-t))$ are involutions, and
- (iv) $A(t) = \frac{-t}{h(-t)}$ and $Z(t) = \frac{d(-t)-1}{h(-t)}$.

Proof. Let $(d(t), h(t))$ be a pseudo-involution. Then $(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (d(t), -h(t))$ is an involution, i.e.,

$$(d(t), -h(t))(d(t), -h(t)) = (d(t)d(-h(t)), -h(-h(t))) = (1, t).$$

Additionally, $-(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (-d(t), -h(t))$ satisfies

$$(-d(t), -h(t))(-d(t), -h(t)) = (d(t), -h(t))(d(t), -h(t)) = (1, t),$$

which implies that $-(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (-d(t), -h(t))$ is also an involution. Hence, we have proven that $(d(t), h(t))$ is a pseudo-involution that implies (i). Equation (ii) follows from (i) because

$$\begin{aligned} I &= ((d(t), h(t))(1, -t)) ((d(t), h(t))(1, -t)) \\ &= (d(t), h(t)) ((1, -t)(d(t), h(t))(1, -t)). \end{aligned}$$

From the above equations, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &(\pm(1, -t)(d(t), h(t))) (\pm(1, -t)(d(t), h(t))) \\ &= ((1, -t)(d(t), h(t))(1, -t)) (d(t), h(t)) = (1, t) = I. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we obtain (iii) from (ii). Similarly, (i) follows from (iii).

To find the A -function and Z -function of a pseudo-involution $(d(t), h(t))$, we recall (see Theorem 3.3 of [27]) the A -sequence of

$$(d_3(t), h_3(t)) = (d_1(t), h_1(t))(d_2(t), h_2(t))$$

has the A -function

$$A_3(t) = A_2(t)A_1\left(\frac{t}{A_2(t)}\right),$$

where $A_1(t)$ and $A_2(t)$ are the A -functions of $(d_1(t), h_1(t))$ and $(d_2(t), h_2(t))$, respectively. Since the A -functions of $(d(t), h(t))$ and $(1, -t)$ are respectively $A(t)$ and -1 , the A -function of $(d(t), h(t))(1, -t)$ is

$$A_3(t) = -A(-t). \tag{20}$$

On the other hand, from Theorem 4.3 of [27] we know the A -function of the involution $(d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (d(t), -h(t))$ is

$$A_3(t) = \frac{t}{-h(t)}. \tag{21}$$

Comparing (20) and (21) we have

$$A(t) = \frac{-t}{h(-t)}.$$

From Theorem 3.4 of [27], the Z -function of

$$(d_3(t), h_3(t)) = (d(t), h(t))(1, -t) = (d(t), -h(t))$$

is $Z_3(t) = Z(-t)$ because the Z -functions of $(d(t), h(t))$ and $(1, -t)$ are $Z(t)$ and 0, respectively. Since $(d_3(t), h_3(t))$ is an involution, from Theorem 4.3 of [27] we also have

$$Z_3(t) = \frac{1 - d(t)}{-h(t)}.$$

Comparing the last two equations, we immediately know

$$Z(t) = \frac{d(-t) - 1}{h(-t)}.$$

From the definitions of A -sequence and Z -sequence, a Riordan array $(d(t), h(t))$ that possesses the above A -function and Z -function is a pseudo-involution. \square

Corollary 1. *Let nonzero $d(t) \in \mathcal{F}_0$ and $h(t) \in \mathcal{F}_1$. Then the infinite lower triangle matrix $(d(t), h(t))$ is a pseudo-involution if and only if*

$$\bar{h}(t) = -h(-t) \text{ and } d(t) = \frac{h(-t)}{h(-t) - td(-t) + t},$$

where the denominator is assumed not to be zero.

Proof. Equation $\bar{h}(t) = -h(-t)$ holds if and only if

$$\frac{t}{\bar{h}(t)} = \frac{-t}{h(-t)},$$

or equivalently, there exists the function $A(t)$ such that

$$A(t) = \frac{t}{\bar{h}(t)} \quad \text{and} \quad A(t) = \frac{-t}{h(-t)},$$

which implies that $(d(t), h(t))$ has an A -function (see, for example, [27]) satisfying (iv) of Theorem 1.

Note that $d(t) = h(-t)/(h(-t) - td(-t) + t)$ if and only if

$$\frac{d(-t) - 1}{h(-t)} = \frac{d(t) - 1}{td(t)},$$

or equivalently, there exists the function $Z(t)$ such that

$$Z(t) = \frac{d(t) - 1}{td(t)} \quad \text{and} \quad Z(t) = \frac{d(-t) - 1}{h(-t)},$$

which implies that $(d(t), h(t))$ has a Z -function (see, for example, [27]) satisfying (iv) of Theorem 1. Combining all above statements together we know that $(d(t), h(t))$ is a pseudo-involution, which completes the proof of Corollary 1. \square

Corollary 1 also presents an algorithm to find a pseudo-involution. Generally, one can accomplish this by carrying through the procedure demonstrated by the following example. For instance, it is clear that $h(t) = t/(1 - t)$ (or $t/(1 + t)$) has the compositional inverse $\bar{h}(t) = t/(1 + t)$ (or $t/(1 - t)$) and satisfies $\bar{h}(t) = -h(-t)$. From Corollary 1, we may also find that $d(t) = 1/(1 - t)$ (or $1/(1 + t)$) satisfies $d(t) = h(-t)/(h(-t) - td(-t) + t)$. Therefore $(1/(1 - t), t/(1 - t))$ (or $(1/(1 + t), t/(1 + t))$) is a pseudo-involution.

Remark. It can be seen that $(d(t), h(t))$ is a pseudo-involution if and only if there exist A -function and Z -function satisfying four relationships:

$$A(t) = \frac{t}{\bar{h}(t)}, \quad A(t) = \frac{-t}{h(-t)}, \quad Z(t) = \frac{d(t) - 1}{td(t)}, \quad \text{and} \quad Z(t) = \frac{d(-t) - 1}{h(-t)},$$

which give not only the formulas shown in Corollary 2 but also the following useful formulas in the construction of pseudo-involutions:

$$h(t) = \frac{tZ(t)}{Z(-t)(1 - tZ(t))} \quad \text{and} \quad d(t) = \frac{h(t)Z(-t)}{tZ(t)}.$$

The proof, which is omitted, is straightforward from the above four relationships.

From (i) and (iii) of Theorem 1 we obtain the following results.

Corollary 2. *Two Riordan arrays $(1/(1-t), t/(1-t)) = \left(\binom{n}{k}\right)_{n,k \geq 0}$ and $(1/(1+t), t/(1+t)) = \left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^{n-k}\right)_{n,k \geq 0}$ are pseudo-involutions. Hence, from (i) and (iii) of Theorem 1, we generate the following four Riordan involutions, denoted by $R_1, R_2, R_3,$ and $R_4,$ respectively:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{1-t}, \frac{t}{1-t}\right) (1, -t) = (1, -t) \left(\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{t}{1+t}\right) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{1-t}, \frac{-t}{1-t}\right) = \left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^k\right)_{n,k \geq 0}, \\
 R_2 &= -\left(\frac{1}{1-t}, \frac{t}{1-t}\right) (1, -t) = -(1, -t) \left(\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{t}{1+t}\right) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{t-1}, \frac{t}{t-1}\right) = \left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^{k+1}\right)_{n,k \geq 0}, \\
 R_3 &= (1, -t) \left(\frac{1}{1-t}, \frac{t}{1-t}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{t}{1+t}\right) (1, -t) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{-t}{1+t}\right) = \left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^n\right)_{n,k \geq 0}, \quad \text{and} \\
 R_4 &= -(1, -t) \left(\frac{1}{1-t}, \frac{t}{1-t}\right) = -\left(\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{t}{1+t}\right) (1, -t) \\
 &= \left(-\frac{1}{1+t}, \frac{-t}{1+t}\right) = \left(\binom{n}{k}(-1)^{n+1}\right)_{n,k \geq 0}. \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. *Let R_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) be the Riordan arrays shown in Corollary 2. Then there hold the following four dual relationships, denoted by $D_1, D_2, D_3,$ and $D_4,$ respectively:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_1 : a_n &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k a_k, & D_2 : a_n &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} a_k, \\
 D_3 : a_n &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^n a_k, & D_4 : a_n &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n+1} a_k.
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, $((-1)^n B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are self-dual sequences with respect to D_1 and $D_3,$ respectively, while $(E_n(\frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{2^n})$ and $((-1)^n (E_n(\frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{2^n}))$ are self-dual sequences with respect to D_2 and $D_4,$ respectively.

Proof. Since (see, for example, Apostol [1] and Milton and Stegun [37])

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k = B_n(1) = (-1)^n B_n, \tag{23}$$

we can conclude that $((-1)^n B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are self-dual sequences with respect to D_1 and D_3 , respectively. Similarly, from (9) and $(-1)^n E_n(-x) = -E_n(x) + 2x^n$ (see, for example [1, 37]), the following holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} \left(E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^k} \right) \\ &= -(-1)^n \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \right)^{n-k} E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \frac{1}{2^k} \\ &= -(-1)^n E_n \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2^n} \\ &= E_n \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - 2 \frac{1}{2^n} + \frac{1}{2^n} = E_n \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^n}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n+1} (-1)^k \left(E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^k} \right) \\ &= - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n-k} E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) + (-1)^n \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k \frac{1}{2^k} \\ &= -E_n \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) + (-1)^n \frac{1}{2^n} = (-1)^n \left(E_n \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^n} \right), \end{aligned}$$

completing the proof of the theorem. □

We now consider the *duals of the Bernoulli and the Euler numbers* and the corresponding *duals of the Bernoulli and the Euler polynomials* with respect to the different dual relationships shown in Theorem 2.

Theorem 3. *Let B_n^* be the duals of the Bernoulli numbers B_n with respect to R_1 , and let $B_n^*(x)$ be the corresponding dual Bernoulli polynomials defined by (10). Then for all $n \geq 0$ the following holds:*

$$B_n^*(x) = (-1)^n B_n(-x - 1) \quad \text{and} \quad B_n^* = (-1)^n B_n + n. \tag{24}$$

Proof. From (8) and (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned} B_n^*(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (x)^{n-k} B_k^* = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (x)^{n-k} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} (-1)^j B_j \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} (-1)^j B_j \sum_{k=j}^n \binom{n-j}{k-j} (x)^{n-k} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} (-1)^j B_j (x+1)^{n-j} = (-1)^n B_n(-x - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} B_n^* &= B_n^*(0) = (-1)^n B_n(-1) \\ &= B_n(1) + n = (-1)^n B_n(0) + n, \end{aligned}$$

which implies the second equation of (24). □

Corollary 3. *Let $B_n^*(x)$ be the duals of the Bernoulli polynomials. Then their generating function is*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq 0} B_n^*(x) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= \sum_{n \geq 0} (-1) B_n(-x-1) \frac{t^n}{n!} \\ &= \frac{-te^{(x+1)t}}{e^{-t}-1} = \frac{e^{(x+1)t}}{1 + \frac{1-t-e^{-t}}{t}}. \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Theorem 4. *With respect to the dual relationship D_3 , the duals of numbers $(-1)^n B_n$, denoted by $((-1)^n B_n)^*$, may be written as*

$$((-1)^n B_n)^* = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^n (-1)^k B_k = B_n + (-1)^n n, \tag{26}$$

and the corresponding dual Bernoulli polynomials are

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} ((-1)^k B_k)^* x^{n-k} = B_n(x) - n(x-1)^{n-1}, n \geq 0. \tag{27}$$

With respect to the dual relationship D_4 , the duals of numbers $E_n(1/2) - (1/2)^n$, denoted by $(E_n(1/2) - (1/2)^n)^*$, have the expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \left(E_n\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n\right)^* &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n+1} \left(E_k\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^k\right) \\ &= (-1)^n \left(E_n\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{3^n - 2}{2^n}\right), n \geq 0. \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

The corresponding dual of the Euler polynomials are

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-k} \left(E_k\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^k\right)^* = (-1)^n E_n(-x+1) - 2(x-1)^n + (x-2)^n \tag{29}$$

for $n \geq 0$.

With respect to the dual relationship D_2 , the duals of numbers $(-1)^n (E_n(1/2) - (1/2)^n)$, denoted by $((-1)^n (E_n(1/2) - (1/2)^n))^*$, can be evaluated as

$$\begin{aligned} \left((-1)^n \left(E_n\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2^n}\right)\right)^* &= \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{k+1} (-1)^k \left(E_k\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2^k}\right) \\ &= E_n\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{3^n - 2}{2^n}, \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

and the corresponding dual Euler polynomials are

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-k} \left((-1)^k \left(E_k\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2^k}\right)\right)^* = E_n(x) + (x+1)^n - 2x^n, n \geq 0. \tag{31}$$

Proof. The proofs are directly from the definitions and are omitted. □

3. Generating Functions of Self-dual Number Sequences

In this section we give some structures of self-dual number sequences, which give the characterizations, relationships, and many other properties of the self-dual number sequences. The first half of the following theorem is presented in Prodinger [42].

Theorem 5. [42] Let $a(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n x^n$. Then its coefficient sequence is a self-dual sequence with respect to $D_1 (D_2)$, i.e., it satisfies

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k a_k = a_n \quad (-a_n)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only if $a(x)$ satisfies the equation

$$a\left(\frac{x}{x-1}\right) = (1-x)a(x) \quad (-(1-x)a(x)),$$

respectively.

The coefficient sequence of $a(x)$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to $D_3 (D_4)$, i.e., it satisfies

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^n a_k = a_n \quad (-a_n)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only if $a(x)$ satisfies the equation

$$a\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) = (1+x)a(x) \quad (-(1+x)a(x)),$$

respectively.

Proof. Since the first half of the theorem is given in [42], it is sufficient to prove the second half as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\pm \frac{1}{1+x} a\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) = \pm \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k (-1)^k x^k (1+x)^{-k-1} \\ &= \pm \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k (-1)^k x^k \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \binom{-k-1}{j} x^j \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \pm \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_k (-1)^{k+j} \binom{k+j}{j} x^{k+j} \\
 &= \pm \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left((-1)^n \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} a_{n-j} \right) x^n = \pm \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n = \pm a(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is complete. □

Corollary 4. *Let $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be a given sequence with ordinary generating function $a(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n x^n$. Then*

(i) [51] $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_1 if and only if $(2a_{n+1} - a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_2 , and

(ii) $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_3 if and only if $(2a_{n+1} + a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_4 .

Proof. The result shown in (i) is given in [51]. It is sufficient to prove (ii). Let

$$b_n = 2a_{n+1} + a_n$$

with its ordinary generating function $b(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} b_n x^n$. Thus,

$$b(x) = \frac{2(a(x) - a_0)}{x} + a(x) = \frac{x+2}{x} a(x) - \frac{2}{x} a_0,$$

which implies

$$\begin{aligned}
 b\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) &= -\frac{x+2}{x} a\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) + \frac{2}{x}(1+x)a_0 \\
 &= -(1+x) \left(\frac{x+2}{x} \frac{1}{1+x} a\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) - \frac{2}{x} a_0 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$a\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) = (1+x)a(x)$$

if and only if

$$b\left(-\frac{x}{1+x}\right) = -(1+x) \left(\frac{x+2}{x} a(x) - \frac{2}{x} a_0 \right) = -(1+x)b(x).$$

Based on Theorem 5 we have finished the proof. □

Theorem 6. *Let $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be a given sequence with exponential generating function $a^*(x) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n x^n / n!$. Then*

(i) [51] $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_1 if and only if $a^*(x)e^{-x/2}$ is an even function,

- (ii) [51] $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_2 if and only if $a^*(x)e^{-x/2}$ is an odd function,
- (iii) $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_3 if and only if $a^*(x)e^{x/2}$ is an even function, and
- (iv) $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_4 if and only if $a^*(x)e^{x/2}$ is an odd function.

Proof. The results shown in (i) and (ii) are given in [51]. We only need to prove (iii) and (iv) by using a similar argument:

$$\begin{aligned} a^*(-x)e^{-x} &= \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k a_k \frac{x^k}{k!} \sum_{j \geq 0} (-1)^j \frac{x^j}{j!} \\ &= \sum_{k \geq 0} \sum_{j \geq 0} (-1)^{k+j} a_k \frac{x^{k+j}}{k!j!} = \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^n \binom{n}{k} a_k \right) \frac{x^n}{n!}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, if

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^n \binom{n}{k} a_k = a_n \quad \text{and} \quad -a_n,$$

then

$$a^*(-x)e^{-x} = a(x) \quad \text{and} \quad -a(x),$$

respectively. These can be written briefly as

$$a^*(-x)e^{-x/2} = \pm a(x)e^{x/2}.$$

If the case of the positive sign on the right-hand side holds, i.e., (a_n) is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_3 , then $a^*(x)e^{x/2}$ is an even function; while the negative sign holds, or equivalently, (a_n) is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_4 , then the function $a^*(x)e^{x/2}$ is odd. It is easy to see the sufficiencies of (iii) and (iv) are also true. This concludes the proof of the theorem. \square

Sun [51] uses Theorem 6 to derive numerous identities including (i) in the following theorem. Wang [56] uses umbral calculus to extend (i) to (ii). We now survey their results and extend them to (iii) and (iv) for other self-dual sequences.

Theorem 7. *For any function f , we have the following identities:*

- (i) [51] $\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) - (-1)^{n-k} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) a_{n-k} = 0$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_1 ,
- (ii) [56] $\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) + (-1)^{n-k} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) a_{n-k} = 0$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_2 ,

(iii) $\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) - \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{n-j} \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) a_{n-k} = 0$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_3 , and

(iv) $\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) + \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{n-j} \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) a_{n-k} = 0$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if $(a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a self-dual sequence with respect to D_4 .

Proof. The proofs of (iii) and (iv) are similar to the proofs of (i) and (ii) by using either Theorem 6 or umbral calculus. Hence, we omit them. \square

From Theorem 2, we know that $((-1)^n B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $(B_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are self-dual sequences with respect to D_1 and D_3 , respectively. In addition, $(E_n (\frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{2^n})$ and $((-1)^n (E_n (\frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{2^n}))$ are self-dual sequences with respect to D_2 and D_4 , respectively. Therefore, we may use Theorem 7 to obtain the following identities.

Theorem 8. *Let B_n and E_n be the Bernoulli numbers and the Euler numbers, respectively. For any function f , we have the following identities:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left((-1)^{n-k} f(k) - \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) B_{n-k} = 0, \\ & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) + (-1)^{n-k} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) \left(E_{n-k} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^{n-k}} \right) = 0, \\ & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left(f(k) - \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{n-j} \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) B_{n-k} = 0, \quad \text{and} \\ & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left((-1)^{n-k} f(k) + \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} f(j) \right) \left(E_{n-k} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^{n-k}} \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

The first identity of (32) is given in [51].

4. Applications of Dual Sequences to the Bernoulli and the Euler Polynomials

Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, and let

$$\begin{aligned} C_{n,\alpha}(x) &= (-1)^n \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a_k (x - \alpha)^{n-k} \quad \text{and} \\ C_{n,\alpha}^*(x) &= (-1)^n \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a_k^* (x - \alpha)^{n-k}. \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Then we have the following identities about $C_{n,\alpha}(x)$ and $C_{n,\alpha}^*(x)$, which are extensions of the main results shown in Sun [52].

Theorem 9. *Let $C_{n,\alpha}(x)$ and $C_{n,\alpha}^*(x)$ be defined as (33), and let $k, \ell \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x + y + z = 1 + 2\alpha$. Then the following holds:*

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{C_{\ell+j+1,\alpha}(y)}{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{C_{k+j+1,\alpha}^*(z)}{k+j+1} = \frac{a_0 x^{k+\ell+1}}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}. \tag{34}$$

In addition, we have:

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} C_{\ell+j,\alpha}(y) = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} C_{k+j,\alpha}^*(z) \tag{35}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j (\ell+j+1) x^{k-j+1} \binom{k+1}{j} C_{\ell+j,\alpha}(y) \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^j (k+j+1) x^{\ell-j+1} \binom{\ell+1}{j} C_{k+j,\alpha}^*(z) \\ & = (k+\ell+2) \left((-1)^k C_{k+\ell+1,\alpha}(y) + (-1)^\ell C_{k+\ell+1,\alpha}^*(z) \right). \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Proof. Substituting (33) into the left-hand side of (34) yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \frac{(-1)^j x^{k-j}}{\ell+j+1} \left(a_0 (-1)^{\ell+j+1} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j+1} \right. \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^{\ell+j} a_{i+1} \binom{\ell+j+1}{i+1} (-1)^{\ell+j+1} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j-i} \Big) \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{(-1)^j x^{\ell-j}}{k+j+1} \sum_{r=0}^{k+j+1} (-1)^{k+j+1} \binom{k+j+1}{r} \sum_{i=0}^r a_i \binom{r}{i} (-1)^r (z-\alpha)^{k+j+1-r} \\ & = ca_0 + \sum_{i=0}^{k+\ell} a_{i+1} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \binom{\ell+j+1}{i+1} \frac{(-1)^j x^{k-j}}{\ell+j+1} (-1)^{\ell+j+1} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j+1-(i+1)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{i=1}^{k+\ell+1} a_i \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \sum_{r=i}^{k+j+1} \binom{\ell}{j} \binom{k+j+1}{r} \binom{r}{i} \frac{(-1)^j x^{\ell-j}}{k+j+1} (-z-\alpha)^{k+j+1-r} \\ & = ca_0 + \sum_{i=0}^{k+\ell} \frac{c_i}{i+1} a_{i+1}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$c = \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \frac{(-1)^j x^{k-j}}{\ell+j+1} (-1)^{\ell+j+1} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \sum_{r=0}^{k+j+1} \binom{\ell}{j} \binom{k+j+1}{r} \frac{(-1)^j x^{\ell-j}}{k+j+1} (-z-\alpha)^{k+j+1-r}.$$

The above c will be evaluated later. For c_i , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (-1)^\ell c_i &= \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \binom{\ell+j+1}{i+1} (i+1) \frac{x^{k-j}}{\ell+j+1} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j-i} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \sum_{r=i+1}^{k+j+1} \binom{\ell}{j} \binom{k+j+1}{r} \binom{r}{i+1} (i+1) \frac{(-1)^{\ell-j+1} x^{\ell-j}}{k+j+1} (-z-\alpha)^{k+j+1-r} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \binom{\ell+j}{i} x^{k-j} (y-\alpha)^{\ell+j-i} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} \binom{k+j}{i} (-1)^{\ell-j+1} x^{\ell-j} \sum_{r=i+1}^{k+j+1} \binom{k+j-i}{r-i-1} (-z-\alpha)^{k+j-i-(r-i-1)} \\ &= x^{k+\ell-i} \left[\sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} \binom{\ell+j}{i} \left(\frac{y-\alpha}{x}\right)^{\ell+j-i} - \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} \binom{k+j}{i} (-1)^{\ell-j} \left(1 + \frac{y-\alpha}{x}\right)^{k+j-i} \right] = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last step occurs because the expression in the brackets is zero-based on Lemma 3.1 of [52]. Finally, we evaluate c as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c &= (-1)^{\ell+1} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} x^{k-j} \frac{(y-\alpha)^{\ell+j+1}}{\ell+j+1} \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{(-1)^j x^{\ell-j}}{k+j+1} \sum_{r=0}^{k+j+1} \binom{k+j+1}{r} (-z-\alpha)^{k+j+1-r} \\ &= (-1)^{\ell+1} \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} x^{k-j} \int_0^{y-\alpha} t^{\ell+j} dt + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \int_0^{x+y-\alpha} t^{k+j} dt \\ &= (-1)^{\ell+1} \int_0^{y-\alpha} t^\ell (t+x)^k dt + (-1)^\ell \int_0^{x+y-\alpha} t^k (t-x)^\ell dt \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (-1)^\ell \left(- \int_x^{x+y-\alpha} (s-x)^\ell s^k ds + \int_0^{x+y-\alpha} (t-x)^\ell t^k dt \right) \\
 &= (-1)^\ell \int_0^x (t-x)^\ell t^k dt = (-1)^\ell \int_0^1 (tx-x)^\ell (tx)^k x dt \\
 &= x^{k+\ell+1} \int_0^1 (1-t)^\ell t^k dt = x^{k+\ell+1} \frac{\Gamma(k+1)\Gamma(\ell+1)}{\Gamma(k+\ell+2)} \\
 &= \frac{x^{k+\ell+1}}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By taking a partial derivative with respect to y on the both sides of (34) and noting $z = 1 + 2\alpha - x - y$, one may obtain (35). Replacing k and ℓ by $k + 1$ and $\ell + 1$ in equation (35) and taking the partial derivative with respect to y , one may obtain (36). The proof is complete. \square

The following corollary of Theorem 9 are analogies of the results shown in Theorems 1.1 and 1.2 of [52].

Corollary 5. *Let $C_{n,0}(x)$ and $C_{n,0}^*(x)$ be defined as (33), and let $k, \ell \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x + y + z = 1$. Then the following holds:*

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{C_{\ell+j+1,0}(y)}{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{C_{k+j+1,0}^*(z)}{k+j+1} = \frac{a_0 x^{k+\ell+1}}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}. \tag{37}$$

In addition, we have

$$\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} C_{\ell+j,0}(y) = \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} C_{k+j,0}^*(z) \tag{38}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^j (\ell+j+1) x^{k-j+1} \binom{k+1}{j} C_{\ell+j,0}(y) \\
 &+ \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j (k+j+1) x^{\ell-j+1} \binom{\ell+1}{j} C_{k+j,0}^*(z) \\
 &= (k+\ell+2) \left((-1)^k C_{k+\ell+1,0}(y) + (-1)^\ell C_{k+\ell+1,0}^*(z) \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

If $a_k = B_k$ or $(-1)^k B_k$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(-1)^{\ell+1} \sum_{j=0}^k x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{B_{\ell+j+1}(y)}{\ell+j+1} + (-1)^{k+1} \sum_{j=0}^\ell x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{B_{k+j+1}(z)}{k+j+1} \\
 &= \frac{x^{k+\ell+1}}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}. \tag{39}
 \end{aligned}$$

In addition, we have

$$(-1)^\ell \sum_{j=0}^k x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} B_{\ell+j}(y) = (-1)^k \sum_{j=0}^\ell x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} B_{k+j}(z) \tag{40}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^\ell \sum_{j=0}^k (\ell + j + 1) x^{k-j} \binom{k+1}{j} B_{\ell+j}(y) \\ & + (-1)^k \sum_{j=0}^\ell (k + j + 1) x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell+1}{j} B_{k+j}(z) \\ & = (k + \ell + 2) \left((-1)^k B_{k+\ell+1}(y) + (-1)^\ell B_{k+\ell+1}(z) \right). \end{aligned}$$

The conjugate Bernoulli polynomials $\tilde{B}_n(x)$ are introduced in [25] by using their generating function shown below:

$$\frac{e^{xt}}{1 + \frac{1+t-e^t}{t}} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \tilde{B}_n(x) \frac{t^n}{n!}. \tag{41}$$

Here the first few terms of the conjugate polynomial sequence $(\tilde{B}_n)_{n \geq 0}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}_0(x) &= 1, \\ \tilde{B}_1(x) &= x + \frac{1}{2}, \\ \tilde{B}_2(x) &= x^2 + x + \frac{5}{6}, \\ \tilde{B}_3(x) &= x^3 + \frac{3}{2}x^2 + \frac{5}{2}x + 2, \\ \tilde{B}_4(x) &= x^4 + 2x^3 + 5x^2 + 8x + \frac{191}{30}, \\ \tilde{B}_5(x) &= x^5 + \frac{5}{2}x^4 + \frac{25}{3}x^3 + 20x^2 + \frac{191}{6}x + \frac{76}{3}, \text{ etc.} \end{aligned}$$

Let $(\tilde{B}_n(x))_{n \geq 0}$ be the conjugate Bernoulli polynomial sequence defined by (41), and let the conjugate Bernoulli numbers $(\tilde{B}_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be defined by $\tilde{B}_n = \tilde{B}_n(0)$. Then we may find that

$$\tilde{B}_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^{n-k} \tilde{B}_k \tag{42}$$

for all $n \geq 0$.

We define the dual sequence of the conjugate Bernoulli number sequence with respect to inverse matrix R_1 . Then the corresponding dual polynomial sequence is

$$\tilde{B}_n^*(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^{n-k} \tilde{B}_k^* \tag{43}$$

for all $n \geq 0$. From Theorem 9, we obtain the following results.

Corollary 6. *Let $k, \ell \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x + y + z = 1$. Then the following holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^k \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} x^{k-j} (-1)^{j+1} \frac{\tilde{B}_{\ell+j+1}(-y)}{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} x^{\ell-j} \frac{\tilde{B}_{k+j+1}^*(-z)}{k+j+1} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{k+1} x^{k+\ell+1}}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}, \end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

where $\tilde{B}_n(x)$ are defined by (41), and $\tilde{B}_n^*(x)$ are defined by (43). In addition,

$$(-1)^k \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k}{j} (-x)^{k-j} \tilde{B}_{\ell+j}(-y) = (-1)^\ell \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell}{j} (-x)^{\ell-j} \tilde{B}_{k+j}^*(-z) \tag{45}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^\ell \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{k+1}{j} (-x)^{k-j+1} (\ell+j+1) \tilde{B}_{\ell+j}(-y) \\ & + (-1)^k \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \binom{\ell+1}{j} (-x)^{\ell-j+1} (k+j+1) \tilde{B}_{k+j}^*(-z) \\ &= (k+\ell+2) ((-1)^{\ell+1} \tilde{B}_{k+\ell+1}(-y) + (-1)^{k+1} \tilde{B}_{k+\ell+1}^*(-z)). \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

In (33), substituting $\alpha = 1/2$,

$$a_k = E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2^k}, \quad \text{and} \quad a_k^* = (-1)^k \left(E_k \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{3^k - 2}{2^k} \right), \tag{47}$$

where the duals a_k^* are derived by using (28) of Theorem 4, we obtain

$$A_n(x) = (-1)^n E_n(x) - (-1)^n x^n \quad \text{and} \quad A_n^*(x) = E_n(-x+1) + (2-x)^n - 2(1-x)^n.$$

Hence, Theorem 9 implies the following result.

Corollary 7. *Let $C_{n,\alpha}(x)$ and $C_{n,\alpha}^*(x)$ be defined as (33) with $\alpha = 1/2$, and let $k, \ell \in \mathbb{N}$ and $x + y + z = 2$. For a_k and a_k^* shown in (47), the following holds:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{\ell+1} x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{E_{\ell+j+1}(y)}{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{E_{k+j+1}(-z+1)}{k+j+1} \\ &= (-1)^{\ell+1} \int_0^y t^\ell (t+x)^k dt - \int_0^{x+y} t^k (x-t)^\ell dt + 2 \int_0^{x+y-1} t^k (x-t)^\ell dt. \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

In addition, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (-1)^\ell \sum_{j=0}^k x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} E_{\ell+j}(y) - (-1)^\ell y^\ell (x+y)^k \\
 = & \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} E_{k+j}(1-z) + (x+y)^k (-y)^\ell - 2(x+y-1)^k (1-y)^\ell.
 \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

The above identities of polynomial sequences can be used to establish identities of number sequences. For instance, if $x = 1$, $y = 0$, and $z = 1$, then (48) yields the following number sequence identity:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{\ell+1} x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{E_{\ell+j+1}(0)}{\ell+j+1} \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{E_{k+j+1}(0)}{k+j+1} = -\frac{1}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ and $y = z = 1/2$, from (48) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{\ell+1} x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{E_{\ell+j+1}(1/2)}{\ell+j+1} + \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{E_{k+j+1}(1/2)}{k+j+1} \\
 = & -\frac{1}{(k+\ell+1) \binom{k+\ell}{k}} + 2B\left(\frac{1}{2}, k+1, \ell+1\right) - 2B\left(\frac{3}{2}, k+1, \ell+1\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $B(\alpha, a, b) = \int_0^\alpha t^{a-1} (1-t)^{b-1} dt$ is an incomplete beta function. From the last two identities, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{\ell+1} x^{k-j} \binom{k}{j} \frac{E_{\ell+j+1}(1/2) - E_{\ell+j+1}(0)}{\ell+j+1} \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^\ell (-1)^j x^{\ell-j} \binom{\ell}{j} \frac{E_{k+j+1}(1/2) - E_{k+j+1}(0)}{k+j+1} \\
 = & 2\left(B\left(\frac{1}{2}, k+1, \ell+1\right) - B\left(\frac{3}{2}, k+1, \ell+1\right)\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Let A and B be any $m \times m$ and $n \times n$ square matrices, respectively. Cheon and Kim [7] introduce the following notation \oplus for the direct sum of matrices A and B :

$$A \oplus B = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix}. \tag{50}$$

By using the notation \oplus , we may obtain the following results on the conjugate Bernoulli polynomials $\tilde{B}(x)$ defined by (43), which includes the matrix form of Lemma 3.2 of Pan and Sun [39] as a special case.

Theorem 10. *Let n be any positive integer, and let $\tilde{B}(t)$ and $P[t]$ be defined as*

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{B}(t) &:= (\tilde{B}_0(t), \tilde{B}_1(t), \dots) \quad \text{and} \\ P[t] &:= \left(\binom{n}{k} t^{n-k} \right)_{n,k \geq 0}, \end{aligned}$$

respectively. Let $(x) = (1, x, x^2, \dots)^T$, $D = \text{diag}(0, 1, 1/2, \dots)$, and $[X] = [0] \oplus \left[\frac{x^{n-k}}{k} \right]_{1 \leq k \leq n}$, i.e.,

$$[X] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & x & \frac{1}{2} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & x^{n-1} & \frac{x^{n-2}}{2} & \cdots & \frac{1}{n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then we have

$$[X]\tilde{B}(x+y) = P[x]D\tilde{B}(y) + [X](x), \tag{51}$$

which implies

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\tilde{B}_k(x+y)}{k} x^{n-k} = \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{\tilde{B}_l(y)}{l} x^{n-l} + H_n x^n \tag{52}$$

for all $n \geq 0$ shown in [39].

Proof. Noting that $\tilde{B}_0(y) = 1$, the left-hand side of (51) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS of (51)} &= [X]P[x]\tilde{B}(y) \\ &= [X] \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ x + \binom{1}{1}\tilde{B}_1(y) \\ x^2 + \binom{2}{1}x\tilde{B}_1(y) + \binom{2}{2}\tilde{B}_2(y) \\ \vdots \\ x^n + \binom{n}{1}x^{n-1}\tilde{B}_1(y) + \cdots + \binom{n}{n}\tilde{B}_n(y) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= [X] \left(\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ x \\ x^2 \\ \vdots \\ x^n \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \binom{1}{1} \tilde{B}_1(y) \\ \binom{2}{1} x \tilde{B}_1(y) + \binom{2}{2} \tilde{B}_2(y) \\ \vdots \\ \binom{n}{1} x^{n-1} \tilde{B}_1(y) + \cdots + \binom{n}{n} \tilde{B}_n(y) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \right) \\
 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ x \\ (1 + \frac{1}{2})x^2 \\ \vdots \\ (1 + \frac{1}{2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n})x^n \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} + [X] \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \binom{1}{1} \tilde{B}_1(y) \\ \binom{2}{1} x \tilde{B}_1(y) + \binom{2}{2} \tilde{B}_2(y) \\ \vdots \\ \binom{n}{1} x^{n-1} \tilde{B}_1(y) + \cdots + \binom{n}{n} \tilde{B}_n(y) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix},
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second term can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ (\binom{1}{1} + \frac{1}{2} \binom{2}{1}) \tilde{B}_1(y)x + \frac{1}{2} \binom{2}{2} \tilde{B}_2(y) \\ \vdots \\ (\binom{1}{1} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n} \binom{n}{1}) \tilde{B}_1(y)x^{n-1} + (\frac{1}{2} \binom{2}{2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n} \binom{n}{2}) \tilde{B}_2(y)x^{n-2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n} \binom{n}{n} \tilde{B}_n(y) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \\
 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \binom{2}{1} \tilde{B}_1(y)x + \frac{1}{2} \binom{2}{2} \tilde{B}_2(y) \\ \vdots \\ \binom{n}{1} \tilde{B}_1(y)x^{n-1} + \frac{1}{2} \binom{n}{2} \tilde{B}_2(y)x^{n-2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n} \binom{n}{n} \tilde{B}_n(y) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the last step we use the identities $\frac{1}{n} \binom{n}{k} = \frac{1}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \binom{n}{k} &= \binom{n-1}{k-1} + \binom{n-1}{k} = \binom{n-1}{k-1} + \binom{n-2}{k-1} + \binom{n-3}{k} = \cdots \\
 &= \binom{n-1}{k-1} + \binom{n-2}{k-1} + \cdots + \binom{k}{k-1} + \binom{k}{k}
 \end{aligned}$$

for $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq k \leq n$. Since the last matrix can be written as $P[x]DB(y)$, we obtain (51). By accomplishing the multiplications of the matrices in (51) and using them in (52), we find that the left-hand side of (52) can be written as

$$LHS \text{ of (52)} = H_n x^n + \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{\tilde{B}_l(y)}{l} x^{n-l} = \sum_{l=1}^n \binom{n}{l} \frac{\tilde{B}_l(y)}{l} x^{n-l} + H_n x^n,$$

which is the right-hand side of (52). □

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